

ANALYSIS OF NOUNS IN THE ARABIC LANGUAGE REGARDING THE COLOR FIELD, THEIR STEMS AND THE MEANINGS OF SYNONYMS (“الوسيط المعجم” BASED ON THE WORK OF” (“PERFECT EXPLANATORY DICTIONARY”)¹

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the analysis of scientific opinions on the substantiations of the color field in the Arabic language on the basis of comments made in the work “المعجم الوسيط” (“Perfect explanatory dictionary”). The author tried to scientifically analyze the views expressed by scientists in the article on what is substantiation, the nature of the phenomenon of substantiation in general linguistics. Consequently, the words related to the color field also refer to the qualities of their roots and their analogues, their variety of meanings, as a scientific source, use “المعجم الوسيط” (“Perfect explanatory dictionary”). The volume of the examples given and the literature used suggest that the phenomenon of substantiation in Arabic, described in the article, is an important contribution to the disclosure of the morphological and syntactic essence of words, especially those that relate to the color field.*

Keywords: *arabic; color field; substantiates; phenomenon of substantiation; morphology; lexicon.*

Substantivity or substantivization is Latin *Substantivum* - gives the meaning of a group of words and usually indicates the conjugation of other groups of words - adjective, number, pronoun, adverb, adjective, as a result of which they denote a direct object. and "who?" or "what?" answers their questions. The case of substantivization occurs in transposition in some situations. In this case, it deviates from its original morphological-syntactic relationship in terms of meaning through the way of word formation in non-morphological style.

At the level of synchronic morphology and syntactic justification of the problems of word formation, the partial belonging of a word to a word group means that its grammatical meaning depends on the syntactic nature. It is from this point of view that A.A. Shakhmatov explains the phenomena of substantiveness in language, including their justification [1]. A.M. Peshkovsky's views have a tendency towards a diachronic approach to the study of the phenomena of word formation, to the statement of the facts of the history of language. From this point of view, A.M. Peshkovsky considered in detail [2] the phenomenon of substantivity - the manifestation of "replacement of word groups" - the issue of substantivization of adjectives and identified the main methods of this process. N.N. Durnovo draws attention to the generality of the paradigms of adjectives and nouns, and the scientist's conclusions break the traditional views on the complete differentiation of these grammatical categories [4].

V.V. Vinogradov explains the phenomenon of substantivity in detail from the morphological, syntactic and lexical point of view and confirms its importance in the grammatical structure of the language [5]. Thus, the scientist talks about the close relationship between nouns

¹ Translations in the article were carried out by the researcher

and adjectives: "the category of nouns in its system includes the former forms of adjectives (tailor, messenger, horseman, private, kitchen, deaf-mute, servant, guard, toilet, fried, mammal, invertebrate, etc.) V.V. Vinogradov said, thereby explaining the syntactic use of adjectives in the role of nouns on the basis of substantive substantive . The considered works also describe the idea of activating the formation of new bases and their stylistic change in the practice of 20th century word groups. We can say that this rule serves as a starting point for us to identify modern neologisms and study the issue of stylistic labeling of studied lexemes.

In the 60s and 80s of the 20th century, the attention of researchers of various fields and scientific schools was focused on the problem of substantiveness, and the grammatical essence of the phenomenon was mainly studied. It is during this period that the main works devoted to this topic are: the problem of word formation methods on synchronic and diachronic bases, and in particular, the morphological and syntactic method of word formation; the issue of word formation motivation, the generality of linguistic and extralinguistic factors affecting word and semantics, grammatical features of lexemes; issues such as the intraverbal form of the word and the possibility of the text formation of the unit were investigated.

In recent years, the phenomenon of substantivity and its justification has become the research topic of many dissertations. They mainly discussed issues of comparative linguistics. However, against the background of almost three hundred years of research on the justification of substantivity in science, many problems have not yet been fully resolved, and a number of issues remain controversial. Thus, there are different views on the phenomenon of substantivity as a way of forming words. There is no single point of view on the nature of words, no general point of view has been reached on their classification according to the level of "substantiation". It is still relevant to study the semantic side of the justification of the phenomenon of substantivity, the essence of which is to ensure the need of a person to express his thoughts with existing linguistic means without creating units with a new morphemic content. It is also very important to determine the functional and stylistic label of the phenomenon of substantivity as full-fledged units of expression and expression of the native speaker's thoughts and feelings . All this indicates the relevance of studying the phenomenon of substantivity in modern linguistics. In general, the following can be stated about the event of substantiveness [6]:

1. Substantivity - it is an effective lexical and grammatical event resulting from a complex of morphological, semantic, and syntactic factors.

2. Substantivity as a grammatical fact has an ancient history and mainly determines the development of modern grammatical categories of adjective and noun .

3. There are various substantivity that occurs through many mechanisms, often due to extralinguistic factors (communicative situation, speech task of oral and written dialogue participants, specific features of individual thinking, socio-political situation, etc.).

4. Substantiveness in modern speech practice has a great functional and methodological potential : they participate in the creation of an imaginary system of artistic works; implements informational and emotional functions of language ; they are thematically specialized elements in the language of working documents.

5. Substantives work as structural units of various terminological systems of scientific speech; reflects the attitude to the worldview and socio-cultural requirements of the society, is often considered a " sign " of the times.

6. Currently, the semantic classification of substantive is expanding due to the emergence of new lexical-semantic groups (means of communication) or their filling with new units.

Another aspect is noticeable in the study of the phenomenon of substantivity in direct Arabic. The distribution of word groups in Arabic is not the same as in Uzbek, Russian or European languages. It is known that word groups in Arabic are divided into three types.

وهو ما دل على اسم (انسان - حيوان - نبات - جماد - صفة - بلد او غير : الاسم تنقسم الكلمة الى ثلاثة أنواع هي : مثال/ (حسن - ابراهيم - سعاد - اسد - جمل - زهرة - فول - مدرسة - طائرة - جميل - طويل - مصر - السودان ذلك من الاسماء (ملحوظة) من الاسماء أيضا : (اسم الاشارة - الضمائر - الاسماء من علامات الاسم : (ال) - (ة) - (التنوين) الخ) الفعل الماضى : مثل :- (شرب - قرأ - فتح - قالت : وهو كل كلمة تدل على عمل معين فى زمن ومن الافعال : الفعل الموصولة) - كتبت - سمعت) - الفعل المضارع (المستمر) : مثل :- (أسمع - أفهم - نشرب - نقرأ - يفتح - يلعب - تكتب - تذاكر) وهو كل لفظ لا يظهر معناه الا مع غيره ومن حروف الجر (من : الحرف فعل الامر : مثل :- (اكتب - اسمع - قل - صلى) ، الى ، عن ، على ، فى ، ل ، ب ، ك) [7]

Translation: Word groups are divided into three types, they are: Nouns: (human, animal, plant, objects, qualities, cities, etc.) are nouns that denote things. Example: Hasan, Ibrahim, Suad, lion, camel, flower, word, school, airplanes, long, Egypt, Sudan and so on. The signs (categories) of the noun: definite article, "ta marbuta", tanwin (taking), as well as demonstrative pronouns and mawsula nouns belong to the noun word group. Verbs: are words that express an action at a specific time. Mozy verb (past tense) for example: drank, read, opened, said, heard. Muzori' verb (present-future tense) for example: I hear, I understand, we drink, we read, we open, we play, you write, you remember. Command verb: example: write, hear, say, pray. Letter (word group): words that have meaning only when they occur with other word groups (prefixes, conjunctions, prepositions and modal words) for example: from, to, about, on, in, for, with, like.

Paying attention to this morphological feature, according to the morphology of the Uzbek language, word groups such as distributed nouns, adjectives, numbers, pronouns, adverbs, and adjectives are part of the noun group. Accordingly, as soon as we say that the naming of an adjective in a syntactic connection creates the phenomenon of substantivity, the noun and the adjective belong to the same "name" group of words. As an example, the possessor of the simple verb phrase "جاء الأحمر" ("Red came") (is morphologically a word belonging to the "red" adjective group. But this word is used in the sentence. "Who came?" "Red has arrived" is the answer. Or: "يا أحمد أنظر إلى الجميل" ("Hey Ahmed, look at the beautiful") "beautiful" is morphologically an adjective, but in the sentence it takes the status of an instrumental complement. Here is an example of the transposition of the transposed words: "يا ابن الواقف تعالى هنا" ("O son of the standing (man), come this way"). "واقف" ("standing", "standing") is a definite adjective, forming an addition compound with the word. In this case, the "ابن" adjective is used and participates in the sentence as "muzof ilayh" - "subordinate word" in relation to the word "ابن", which has fulfilled the function of possessor.

Above, we observed that the quality الأحمر ("red") appears in the possessive function of the sentence. The root of this word is "حمر". In dictionaries, chapter II of the verb "حَمَرَ" [hammara] – "to paint red"; It is given in such meanings as "to fry", "to fry". Also, chapter V "تَحَمَّرَ" [tahammara] form - "to turn red"; "paint" for example lips; It means "to fry", "to fry". Also, Chapter IX means "إِحْمَرَّ" [ihmarra] "to be red", "to blush" [8].

It is worth noting that the forms of words denoting colors in different patterns are interesting because they indicate different meanings, including the meanings of the following words from this root:

حَمَار	hamma:r(un)	feed the donkey
جمار، حمير	hima:r(un), [hami:r]	donkey
حَمَارَة	hammarat(un)	heat
حَمْر	hamr(un)	red clay
حُمْر	humr(un)	bitumen, asphalt
حُمَيْرَاء	humayra:u	measles
يحمور	yahmu:r(un)	hemoglobin

As can be seen from the examples, the semantic categories of nouns formed from the root meaning "red" in Arabic are significantly wider.

It is natural that this diversity creates some difficulties when learning a language, especially the problem of keeping words in memory in terms of their meaning and pronunciation. However, it should be noted that the root meaning of the word depends largely on the acquisition of commonalities. Also, in order to memorize the meaning of the words made from the root, it is necessary to quote sentences with them, especially proverbs, short texts consisting of interesting questions and answers. As an example, [9] "أنا أمير وأنت أمير من يسوق الحمير" ("I am amir and you are amir, who feeds the herd").

It is also important to pay attention to the fact that the meaning of the stem is compatible with the meaning of the words that are formed from it. Let's pay attention to the comments made in the work "المعجم الوسيط" ("The perfect dictionary") in the following places :

(حَمَرَ) الشَّيْءُ حُمْراً: قَشَرَهُ. فهو محمور، وحمير. ويُقال: حمّر الأرض، وحمّر السَّيْرَ من الجلد. و - الرأس والشعر والوصوف والوبر: حلّقه. و - الشاة ونحوها: سلخها. [10]

Translation: A clear red thing: to peel, peel something and it is mahmur (red) and hamir (red). It is said that the man used to redden, he skinned and shaved his hair, he shaved the wool or hairs, he took the wool from the goat and the things that grew on it, and skinned it.

(حَمَرَ) الفرس ونحوه - حَمَرًا: اتَّخَمَ من أكل الشَّعِيرِ. و - تَغَيَّرَت رَائِحَةُ فَمِهِ منه الدَّابَّةُ: صارت من السَّيْمَنِ كالحمار ثلاثة. و [10].- فلانٌ: تحرق غضباً وغيظاً. ويقال: حَمَرَ عليه. فهو حَمَرٌ

Translation: Red (horse and the like - red herbivores). And the smell of the creeper's mouth changed: he grew fat like an ass giving birth. So-and-so: burns with anger and rage - means: he blushed and he blushed.

(المِحْمَرُ) : ما يقشّر أو يُسلخ أو يُحلق : به من حديدة ونحوها . و - من الرجال : اللئيم - و - من الخيل : الذي يشبه الحمار في جريه - و - الفرس الهجين . (ج) محاميرٌ ، ومحاميرٌ. [10]

Translation: Refined with iron and the like, skin or beard (muzakkar), an average horse, a donkey-like horse - a hybrid mare (mule).

Paying attention to the comments, it can be felt that the creators of the dictionary have approached based on the principle of shortness and clarity. They also mentioned the use of words according to gender and number categories. The dictionary approaches every word from this point of view.

Let's take a look at another color definition:

(عَاجٌ) - عَوْجاً: رَجَع . و - عن الأمر: انصرف . ويقال : ما عاج بكلام فلان: ما التفتت إليه ولا اكرثت له. وفلان ما يعوج عن الشَّيْء: ما يرجع عنه . و بالمكان وفيه: أقام . و على المكان: عَطَفُ. و- الشَّيْء عَوْجاً ، وعجاجاً : ثناه وأماله. يقال: عاج رأس البعير بالزمام.

(عوج) العود ونحوه - عَوْجًا: مال و - انحنى و - الأرض: لم تَسْتَو. و - الطريق: التوى و -الإنسانُ عَوْجًا: ساءَ خُلُقُه. و - انحرف دينه . ويقال: قول به عَوْج: منحرف عن القصد ، وقولٌ غيرُ ذى عَوْج: مستقيم سليم. وفي التنزيل العزيز: (قُرْآنًا عربيًّا غيرِ ذى عَوْجٍ) فهو أعوج وهي عوجاء. (ج) عوج.[10]

Translation: to pass, to cross, to return. About this: So-and-so's words are meaningless. It doesn't matter what he says. Inaccuracy in something. Something is crooked and not straight. Return, crooked return, twisted, crooked man: his creation is evil. His apostasy. They also say: not crooked - that is, straight and healthy.

As it is said in the Qur'anic verse: "The Arabic Qur'an is free of crookedness." " " عوج in plural , " عوجاء " in muannas, " عوج " in plural.

This word, which means Tusni, also indicates a number of meanings when it is put into patterns. In general, the comments given in "Komus" are considered as an important source for Arabic language scholars to understand modern and historical words, as well as words used in Arabic dialects . It can be said that the use of color and color words in particular serves to have a clear idea of the field.

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